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ZAMONAVIY DUNYONING IJTIMOIY MANZARASI VA JAMIYAT TUZILMALARI TRANSFORMATSIYASI

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MAQOLADA KELITIRILGAN DALILLARNING TO'G'RILIGI UCHUN MUALLIF MAS'ULDIR | АВТОР НЕСЕТ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬ ЗА ДОСТОВЕРНОСТЬ ФАКТОВ ИЗЛОЖЕННЫХ В СТАТЬЕ

развитием общества на основе концепции «Новый Узбекистан – просвещенное общество», а также принципами верховенства закона и справедливой социальной политики, которые станут ключевыми принципами работы государственных органов. В новом курсе по-прежнему приоритетное внимание будет уделяться развитию экономики, частного бизнеса, человеческого капитала и привлечению иностранных инвестиций.

Инициатива о внесении изменений и дополнений в Конституцию Республики Узбекистан и проведенная на этом направлении работа была в полном соответствии со стратегическими задачами построения Нового Узбекистана. С одной стороны, поправки зафиксировали те изменения, которые уже произошли, а с другой, содержат ориентиры для дальнейшего развития и будут программой действий.

Принятие «Стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана» и внесенные дополнения в Конституцию отчетливо показывают, что реформы принимают необратимый характер, ставя перед собой новые масштабные цели и задачи, позитивные результаты от реализации которых должны в ближайшие годы ощутить на себе как каждый гражданин Узбекистан, так и общество, и государство в целом.

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INTEGRITY AS AN ACTUAL DIRECTION IN THE SOCIOLOGY OF SPORT

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Abstract: By the decision of UNESCO since 2002 the third Thursday of November has been declared the World Philosophy Day, this day is celebrated in more than 70 UNESCO Member States. Since 2010, at the initiative of the St. Petersburg Philosophical Society, Philosophy Days have been included in the official list of St. Petersburg holidays and memorable dates, and in 2020 year they are held on November 19-21. In the days of philosophy in the framework of the XII International Conference "Theoretical and Applied Ethics: Traditions and Perspectives", organized in St. Petersburg State University, on November 21, a round table on the theme «Conceptualization of sports integration: multiple practices and approaches» was held. The interest in this topic was dictated by the growing attention of international sports organizations to the principles of honesty and integrity of sport and by the response of leading representatives of modern sociology of sport. The increasing tendencies of consumerism, medialization, and commercialization of sport set new practical tasks for its social regulation and institutional organization.

Keywords: Round table, sport, integrity, Fair Play, ethics, commercialization sociology of sports.

ИНТЕГРИТИ КАК АКТУАЛЬНОЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ В СОЦИОЛОГИИ СПОРТА

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Аннотация: По решению ЮНЕСКО с 2002 года третий четверг ноября объявлен Всемирным днем философии, этот день отмечается более чем в 70 странах-членах ЮНЕСКО.

С 2010 года по инициативе Санкт-Петербургского философского общества Дни философии включены в официальный перечень праздников и памятных дат Санкт-Петербурга, а в 2020 году проводятся 19-21 ноября. В дни философии в рамках XII Международной конференции "Теоретическая и прикладная этика: Традиции и перспективы", организованной в Санкт-Петербургском государственном университете, 21 ноября состоялся круглый стол на тему "Концептуализация спортивной интеграции: многочисленные практики и подходы". Интерес к данной теме продиктован растущим вниманием международных спортивных организаций к принципам честности и порядочности спорта и откликом ведущих представителей современной социологии спорта. Усиливающиеся тенденции консьюмеризации, медиализации и коммерциализации спорта ставят новые практические задачи его социального регулирования и институциональной организации.

Ключевые слова: круглый стол, спорт, честность, честная игра, этика, социология коммерциализации спорта.

Institute of Philosophy, Saint-Petersburg University (Russia) celebrates its 80th anniversary. The Institute is the one of most important centers of philosophy in Russia. Several scholar schools have been formed within the walls of the Institute and the Saint-Petersburg ethical school is one of them. The tradition of running international ethical conferences at Saint-Petersburg University began in 2007. The permanent team was built in the previous years and it allows implementing the scientific and publishing partnership. The conference has wide spread geography: Russia (St. Petersburg, Moscow, Novosibirsk, Yekaterinburg, Murmansk etc.) Lithuania, Finland, Spain, USA, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, Italy, France, Belarus, Poland, Slovakia, Japan, Iran and Kuwait. The mission of the conference is the historical analysis of ethical categories as well as the research of the most important moral phenomena of present-day society and current issues of practical philosophy and applied ethics. In 2020 a round table on the theme « Conceptualization of sports integration: multiple practices and approaches" was held.

In the modern sports life of the society, the problem denoted by the term "integrity" has gained increasing importance [1]. It concerns moral integrity, purity of ideals, and unity of sport principles. Integrity of sport consists of social relations among sportsmen but it is conditioned by many subject social institutions and organizations of the sport life of the society. The existing problem is deeply social in nature and requires a special sociological approach [2]. Absence of common practices of regulation and maintenance of integrity deprives sport of its fundamental quality — equality of chances to win. In case of weakness in sport there are such destructive phenomena as the use of prohibited drugs (doping), contractual results of competitions, manifestation of cruelty to rivals, personality trailing by gender and age parameters, corruption of sport organizations, etc.

The problem is particularly acute in Russian sports. The existence of sport in Russia is strongly influenced by two different processes. On the one hand, the commodification of all social relations is increasing [3]. On the other hand, the policy of national identity strengthening is becoming more active. The existing problem is conditioned by the fundamental transformation of the social system and formation of a new national identity. The legal and moral consciousness of the society affects the values that play a decisive role in the construction of such identity [4]. Therefore, the solution of the problem is not in the plane of individual measures, but is determined by a set of interrelated measures. This requires, first of all, a theoretical justification based on the experience of several social disciplines (sociology, ethics, law). Against this background, the round table is of acute social and scientific importance.

The round table was attended by leading international specialists in the field of sports sociology from Taiwan, India and the USA, as well as teachers, sociologists and lawyers of St. Petersburg State University.

The first speaker was Sun Chia-Tinga with the topic "Acceptance of Genetic Doping as a Way of Thinking: Ethical Dilemmas and Challenges in Modern Sport. The speaker from Taiwan identified the problem of doping at a new level, namely the problem of "gene doping". The essence of this problem is that with the development of genetic engineering technology, in the last 10-15 years, there

has been a scientific breakthrough in this field. This subsequently had an impact on the potential of the human body, namely on its biomedical effects. Together with the development of genetic engineering, in particular with its application in sports activities, there was no transformation and development in the field of sports law. Consequently, the achievements of science in the field of genetic engineering have proven to be a significant challenge for sports law, as well as for sports ethics, which is still adapted to the principles of Aristotelian ethics, a social form of moral consciousness.

The contemporary challenges that sport ethics now faces have come rather unexpectedly to it. The divide between doping and permitted stimulants in professional sport tends to narrow by the day. In the cutting-edge scientific literature of recent years, it is written that a number of national sports federations have begun to see trends related to increasing control in the use of genetic technologies in sport. After an analysis of the main possible methods and practices for combating the restriction of the use of genetic doping, the success of this or that method should be noted as an increase in control at the genetic level, so changes in attitudes towards genetic doping are primarily related to changes in the entire system of the axiology of sport, its values and forms of management. This presentation also emphasized the importance of cultural, value and behavioral specificities of different countries in the process of adaptation to new gene technologies.

The next hot topic of the day was presented by Ilya Vasiliev, Associate Professor at St. Petersburg State University. His topic was "Sports jurisprudence against a narrow understanding of integrity. The speaker reasonably emphasized the peculiarities of jurisprudence in matters of sports integration. It was noted that a number of sports lawyers, when talking about integration in sports, focus on the principles of *Lex sportiva*. These principles are based on the peculiarities of sport specificity, which thus makes them different from fundamental and other branch principles of law. Despite this, the unity of essence understanding of the integration of sport is far from consensual. Despite certain agreements of a number of sports lawyers associated with the forced view of sports principles that reflect a narrow view of the issues raised. Ilya Vasiliev proposed, when considering the above question, to derive integration in sport from the opposite, namely not from the rules and regulations, but from the violations and challenges to the special values in sport, those values that act as the foundation in the pyramid of management in sport. The speaker believes that it is through this approach that it will be possible to identify the influence of different forms of denotation of concepts for the concept put forward, including such concepts in sport as honesty and purity and others. In conclusion, the author concluded that the lack of unity in the understanding of the integration of sport and sport violations related to honesty in sport and the "purity" of athletes represent a risk of the growth of hidden illegitimate interests in sport. A discussion of this presentation was sparked by the issue related to the relationship between national and international statistics in the manipulation of results in individual sports.

The next presentation was given by Emese Ivan from the USA. The topic of her presentation was: "Game Changers in Sports: The Ethics of Innovation, Creativity and Entrepreneurship. The message of the presentation was related to the flexible moral imperatives of today's sport associated with the constant changes in sporting practices. With the development of new technologies, the behavioral patterns of athletes are also changing, which requires new knowledge and ways of perceiving changes in moral consciousness, sport ethics, and the influence of the latter on the expected/unexpected behavior of athletes in sports games. All of this necessitates the development of new models related to sports entrepreneurship. One of the most key representatives of the development of entrepreneurial mentality in sports is three directions. The first such direction is actions related to innovative development and a new understanding of the role of ethics in sport. This suggests that there is a deliberate approach to the integration of entrepreneurship in sports ethics; in particular this is related to the proactive strategies of sports organizations addressing the perceived ethical problems of today and their possible manifestations in the future. The second direction can be characterized by unplanned or accidental forms of entrepreneurship that have emerged in sport ethics. This kind of entrepreneurship arises in the case of spontaneous changes associated with an inevitable ethical response to technological innovations and the forms of development of these innovations.

However, due to the lack of an institutional form of change in technological development, there is no strategy for the development of moral regulators in sport ethics. The third direction is considered evolutionary forms of entrepreneurship in sports ethics. These changes are associated with a certain social environment, included in the system of influence of interrelated institutions based on the values and features of culture in sport.

An interesting presentation was given by Indian colleagues Sanjay Tewari and Sanjana Tewari. Their presentation was entitled "Fixing: The Threat to the Integrity of Indian Sport. The presentation of Indian colleagues focused on the consideration of "rigged" competitions, which distort the basic principle of sport, namely the principle of "play" associated with unexpected outcomes and results of the contest. The speakers emphasized the increasing transformation of sport and its increasing transition into the sphere of entertainment, where the material component of sports practices and the mass media begin to play a key role. To illustrate the hypothesis, the speakers considered the example of a professional soccer cricket league in India, where wealthy businessmen invest a large amount of financial resources into sports competitions in order to profit from the entertainment of sports audiences. The latter becomes fertile ground for the development of corruption, forms of fraud and bookmaking, which is extremely damaging to the values of sports. The speakers concluded that to solve such problems it is necessary to develop an effective legislative base and legal instruments of social regulation. At the end of the presentation a program of effective measures to develop tools to influence the social institutions of Indian society to such changes in the sports industry was proposed.

Aleksandr Gonashvili in his report "The role of Fair Play in shaping sports practices" emphasized that nowadays recognition of sportsmen's achievements requires both material and social support so that expenses and rewards from the state and/or society could serve as a form of recognition of social value of such achievements. The author noted that sport is increasingly becoming a form of market relations and is no longer a form of leisure but a part of labor, where one of the factors of production is human potential and the product is the sporting result. The attitude towards sport as an element of industrial civilization is a countercultural phenomenon in contrast to the original philosophy and culture of sport, which was proclaimed by Pierre de Coubertin and which is the basic principle of the Olympic Charter. Shifting the emphasis on sports ethics in the past and present, the author noted that the connecting link between these periods is the principle of fair play (Fair Play). The author concluded that the principles of Fair Play are signs of counterbalancing egoism of athletes in sport. Moral and ethical attributes of Fairplay are those forms of manifestation of sport that makes sport not a means of production and consumption of the maximum physical capacity, but makes it part of cultural and spiritual values.

The discussion was concluded with a presentation by Professor Mikhail Sinyutin of St. Petersburg State University on "Contradiction in the Definition of Sports Integrity as an Expression of Real Social Contradiction: Statement of the Question. The outgoing, examined the theoretical issues related to values in sports. The author put forward the hypothesis that the contradiction of values in sport is not related to the negative or positive forms of values, but to the contradictory, ambivalent understanding in the scientific literature of sport and its forms. The peculiarity of this contradiction lies in the nature of sports values, where on the one hand we are talking about the moral regulation of the behavior of athletes, and on the other hand the legal regulators of sports duration associated with the public manifestation of sports activity. One of the most subtle features is the transition of elements of the social construction of sport from competition to spectacle or performance. It is in this kind of transition that the contradiction and tendencies of medicalization and consumerism can be traced. Analyzing the documents of the International Olympic Committee the speaker revealed the priority of normative-legal development in these documents.

Summing up all the speeches, the round table participants indicated their hope for international scientific cooperation in the field of ethics, sociology, economics and anthropology of sport, emphasizing the effective element of preparing sports organizations for the new challenges of social reality in sport.

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ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНОЙ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТИ В ЦИФРОВОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ

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Аннотация: Актуальность исследования обусловлена тем, что растет влияние интернета и медиаресурсов, наблюдается тенденция к развитию виртуальных личностей, мало связанных с реальностью и проявляющих черты антисоциального человека. В связи с этим данная статья посвящена исследованию проблемных вопросов, касающихся цифровой идентичности, цифровой самоидентификации личности, цифрового профиля и выявление аспектов и характеристик сетевой личности. Цифровое пространство, виртуальная реальность, сетевая коммуникация, сетевое сознание, сетевая культура задают новое проблемное поле для изучения феномена идентичности личности в условиях цифрового (сетевого) общества.

Ключевые слова: виртуальная личность, самопрезентация, социальные сети, интернет-пространство, социокультурная идентичность.

TRANSFORMATION OF SOCIO-CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE DIGITAL SPACE

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Abstract: The relevance of the study is due to the fact that the influence of the Internet and media resources is growing, there is a tendency towards the development of virtual personalities that have little connection with reality and exhibit the features of an antisocial person. In this regard, this article is devoted to the study of problematic issues related to digital identity, digital self-identification of a person, a digital profile and the identification of aspects and characteristics of a network personality. Digital space, virtual reality, network communication, network consciousness, network

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